

INTERFACE DEBONDINGS IN FOAM CORE SANDWICH BEAMS AND PANELS

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the analysis of debondings in the face/core interface of foam core sandwich beams and panels. The debondings are treated as cracks and analysed using linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM). The finite element (FE) method and a simplified analytical model is used to analyse beams in four-point bending, with finite size interface debondings, as well as uniformly pressure loaded square and circular panels, with embedded circular debondings. Stress intensity factors are computed and compared with fracture toughness data of the core material in order to predict the onset of damage growth. This gives the anticipated reduction in load bearing capacity of the structural member due to the presence of the debonding. Full-scale tests are performed with beams and panels, containing simulated interfacial debondings, for verification of the analysis. The results show that face to core interface debondings have a drastic influence on the load bearing capacity of foam core sandwich structures.

KEYWORDS: Sandwich constructions; Debonding; Foam core; Finite element method; Testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

The adhesive joints bonding the faces to the core material in a sandwich construction ensure that loads are transferred between the components. However, debondings may arise due to errors in the manufacturing process, misuse, or overloading. These will reduce both the stiffness and the load bearing capacity of the sandwich structure. Hence, it is of vital importance not only to detect these flaws but also to quantitatively estimate their influence on structural integrity.

Several authors (1-3) have treated face/core interface debondings in sandwich beams. Triantafillou and Gibson (1) used a double shear specimen to find the toughness of the interface and used this to predict the onset of damage growth in beams with simulated debondings. Carlsson *et al.* (2) presented the cracked sandwich beam (CSB) specimen for measuring the interface toughness. This specimen is used in this paper to extract toughness data. Zenkert (3) used an energy approach to compute the stress intensity of debonding cracks

and found good agreement between predicted and experimentally measured fracture loads for sandwich beams in four-point bending. The methodologies from (3) are used in the present paper and some results are given for the purpose of comparing.

In this investigation three different debonding problems are treated and compared; a beam in four-point bending, illustrated in Fig.1a; a circular and a square panel, illustrated in Fig.1b. The panels have circular embedded interface debondings and they are subjected to a uniform pressure load. Only symmetric sandwiches are treated, *i.e.*, both faces are of the same material and have equal thickness. The aim is to compute the stress intensity factors for the debonding cracks using a simplified analytical model, and compare the model with finite element analysis of several different geometries. By using extracted fracture toughness data for the core material and the interface, a prediction of the load for onset of damage growth is performed.

2. ANALYSIS

2.1 Analytical Approach This section is a brief summary of the analytical approach. Engineering beam and plate theory including transverse shear deformation is employed (4), assuming thin face sandwiches so that deflection due to bending and shear may be superimposed (4). It is also assumed that no contact between the crack surfaces occur. The approach is to estimate the energy release rate through the change in potential energy of the system due to crack extension. The energy release rate for a panel is defined as

$$G = -\partial U/\partial a, \text{ where } U = \int p \, dw \quad (1)$$

a is the crack length, U the strain energy, which in linear elasticity corresponds to the work done by the applied load, p the external pressure, and w the transverse displacement.

A detailed description of the method applied to the beam in four-point bending was given in (3), where it was found to give good correspondence with FE-analysis. The only problem found was to treat the incompatibility in deformations at the cross-section of the debonding crack tip. The approach here, based on the same assumptions as in (1) and (3), is to estimate the additional deformation due to the presence of the debonding crack. For simplification, consider only the circular part of the panel containing the debonding crack. It has radius a and is assumed to have clamped edges, as illustrated in Fig.2. Due to the incompatibility of the clamped edge, corresponding to the cross-section dividing the cracked and the uncracked part of the panel, an additional rotation of this cross-section must be added. This is treated as a shear stiffness reduction acting as a shear lag effect, *c.f.* ref.(3). The load on the cracked panel, p , must be divided between the two panel parts (single face and a bonded face and core). This load division is a function of a , and bending and shear stiffnesses of the panel. When the deformation field is found, for both a cracked and an uncracked panel, the additional work done by the external pressure may be computed as function of crack length, by integrating over the entire panel. Thereby the energy release rate is obtained as in eq.(1). For a bi-material crack (5), the stress intensity factor is

$$G = [(\kappa_c + 1)/\mu_c + (\kappa_f + 1)/\mu_f] K^2/16, \text{ where } K^2 = K_I^2 + K_{II}^2 = G_I + G_{II} \quad (2)$$

κ equals $3-4\nu$ in plane strain, ν is Poisson's ratio, and μ is the shear modulus. Indices f and c refer to face and core, respectively.

2.2 FE-Analysis The stress field in the vicinity of a crack tip situated between two dissimilar materials can be written in the same manner as for the homogenous case, but here the singularity is a complex constant, $1/2 \pm i\epsilon$ (6). This means that in the close vicinity of the crack tip, $r < 0.0001a$ (6), the stresses oscillate with an increasing amplitude and frequency as $r \rightarrow 0$. In analogy with LEFM under small scale yielding conditions, this zone may be disregarded. It was found in (6) that the deformation of a bi-material crack in a shear field produces a very large contact area which must be accounted for.

The FE-technique used here was developed by Smelser (7), which utilizes crack flank displacement data from the FE-analysis to compute stress intensity factors in both Mode I and Mode II. It is based on the theoretically computed deformation field for a bi-material crack. The beam in Fig. 1a was modelled with 408 quadratic membrane elements, and the circular panel, with radius 800 mm, with 336 quadratic rotational symmetric element (this problem is two-dimensional due to rotational symmetry). The square panel offers double symmetry and therefore only one quarter of the panel was modelled, with approximately 400 quadratic shell and 800 volumetric elements, depending on panel geometry. The meshes were refined towards the crack tips and gap constraints were attached to the crack surfaces to prevent overlapping, and, if so, to find the contact forces. The FE-analyses were performed on a Convex C120 with the multi-purpose FE-code ABAQUS.

Twenty-three beam geometries (different materials, thicknesses and crack lengths) were analysed in (3), giving a correspondence with the analytical model within two percent. The portion of Mode I stress intensity was in the order of 1 to 10 percent of the Mode II.

Sixteen different panel geometries were analysed, as described in Table 1, along with the computed stress intensity factors. All panels had simply supported edges, except one with clamped edges. The Mode I stress intensity was only approximately 5 to 15 percent of that of Mode II, for both the circular and the square panels. The stress intensity variations along the crack front in the square panels were negligible for the short cracks, but increasing up to approximately 20 percent from the average value for $a = 250$ mm, with the maximum values along the axes of symmetry. In the beam case it was found that one crack tip opened up (left tip in Fig.1a) after loading and the other closed, which is in accordance with the results in (6). For the panels, the same situation arises, but here it depends on which side the load is applied, closing the crack when the pressure is applied on the same side as the debonding crack and opening the crack tips when applied on the reverse side. Since the FE-evaluation technique used is derived for traction free crack surfaces, the pressure was applied on the opposite side of the debonding crack. Here, the contact area was a circle with radius approximately equal to $0.8a$, leaving an area of radius $0.2a$ from the crack tip open for the circular panels, and an almost entirely open crack in the square panels, leaving enough traction free crack surface to perform the stress intensity calculation. By making two consecutive FE-analyses with slightly different crack lengths, G may be estimated even for closed crack tips. This procedure showed that the total G was approximately the same regardless of the load case. The sign of the Mode II stress intensity will, however, change depending on what side the load is applied, since the sign of the shear stress changes.

As seen from Table 1, the analytical approach corresponds well with FE-calculations of the circular panels. The stress intensities of the square panels are about 10 to 30 percent greater than for the circular panels of the same geometry. It is also seen that the boundary condition of the panel, simply supported or clamped, has very little influence. This is because the transverse force is invariable with the boundary condition and that a significant part of the stress intensity is Mode II. As seen in Table 1, the stress intensity increases with crack length and core modulus and is decreasing with face thickness, core thickness, and face modulus, in accordance with the beam cases (3).

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Material Data Fracture toughness data were found using two different test specimens, schematically illustrated in Fig.3, the end-notch flexure (ENF), with $W = a = 60$ mm, and the cracked sandwich beam (CSB), with $L = 150$ mm, $a = 50$ mm, and a 30 mm thick core. The former specimen was manufactured by bonding two blocks of core material to each other with a thin film of Teflon to simulate a crack. Two 2 mm thick GRP-faces were bonded on each side of the core to prevent the specimen from failing in tension/compression or by local indentation. The CSB specimen was manufactured in the same way but here the simulated debonding crack was placed in the face/core interface. Both aluminum and GRP-faces were used for the CSB specimen. The stress intensity factors were found from FE-calculations and they consist almost of entirely Mode II. More detailed information concerning fracture toughness testing may be found in (3). In short, crack extension may occur in any direction in the ENF specimen since the material surrounding the crack tip has the same toughness. Crack growth occur in a direction approximately 80 degrees from the crack direction, as indicated by the dashed line in Fig.3. In the CSB specimen, on the other hand, crack extension is forced along the interface (see dashed lines in Fig.3). In this context, it is noted that the sign of the Mode II stress intensity will govern whether the crack will extend along the interface or into the core material (3).

The core materials used in this study was Divinycell H60, H100 and H200, where the number corresponds to the nominal density in kilograms per cubic metre. It is a cross-linked cellular Poly(vinyl chloride) foam used in various sandwich constructions. The measured values of the fracture toughness for the two specimens are given in Table 2. It is seen that the CSB specimen gives a higher toughness due to the restraint in propagation direction.

3.2 Predictions Assume first that the total stress intensity is independent of load case, *i.e.*, pressure on upper or lower side, and that the stress intensities may be estimated either by extrapolations of the computed cases in Table 1 or by using the derived analytical model. One might also assume that the stress intensity is purely Mode II when the crack is closed, *i.e.*, the load is applied on the same side as the debonding crack. By studying the deformations at the crack tips it was found that; the sign of the Mode II stress intensity implies crack extension into the core material, in the same manner as in the ENF specimen, when the load is applied on the same side as the debonding crack (upper side), and along the interface when the load is applied on the opposite side (the case when the crack tip opened up), as in the CSB specimen. This corresponds to the right and the left crack tips in the beam case, *c.f.* Fig. 1a, respectively.

By comparing with the results in (3), where the different signs of the Mode II stress intensity of the two crack tips implied dual fracture criteria, the following reasoning may be performed. If the crack tip is open (load on lower side), the crack would want to propagate into the face material. But it cannot, since the face material has a very high toughness and crack propagation is therefore forced along the interface. Crack initiation would occur when the stress intensity reaches the value found from the CSB specimen. Applying the load on the side of the debonding crack (upper side), changes the sign of the Mode II stress intensity and the crack would propagate into the core. Crack initiation would occur as the stress intensity reaches the toughness value from the ENF tests. However, this crack is closed at the tip and subjected to a contact pressure. If there is no, or little friction this prediction would be fairly accurate. If there is much friction, or even locking, it would be conservative.

3.3 Full-scale tests Four different beam geometries and four different square panels were manufactured, described in Table 3. The debonding cracks were simulated by placing a Teflon film in the face/core interface. Aluminum faces were bonded to the core using a Polyurethane adhesive and GRP-faces were hand-laid directly onto the core. Four beams of each geometry were tested, but only one of each panel. The beams were tested in a four-point bending rig in an Instron testing machine. The square panels were tested in a special panel rig where the uniform pressure was applied using a water bag. All test were performed under a prescribed displacement rate.

In the beam tests, the closed right tip (*c.f.* Fig.1a) initiated and propagated unstably a crack, inclined approximately 80 degrees from the crack directions, downward into the core. This verifies that the stress intensity consist of almost pure Mode II. The load-displacement relation was close to linear up to failure. The measured and predicted fracture loads are given in Table 3, along with the ratio of the design load, assuming no crack and static core shear failure, to the measured fracture load. The latter is referred to as the reduction in load bearing capacity. As seen, the correspondence of the predictions is within 20 percent. The scatter in the test results were within a maximum divergence of less than 6 percent from the average value.

The panels were tested with the load applied on the same side as the debonding crack. No catastrophic failure occurred but the panels started emitting small popping sounds as the predicted failure load was approached. In the fracture toughness test specimens, similar popping sound were heard at approximately 90 to 95 percent of the fracture load, probably indicating microscopic failure of cell walls in the vicinity of the crack tip. Hence, one might assume that stable crack growth begins in the panels at a load level where these popping sounds start to occur. Hence, the measured fracture load is a very imprecise estimate due to the difficulties in monitoring the exact load level. The load-deflection relation was linear up to this point after which the stiffness slightly decreased with increasing load. The mid-point deflection at failure was in the order of 0.5 to 1 of the panel thickness which for a sandwich is within the region where small deformation theory is valid (8), and the load was below the point where the core may become plastic in its stress-strain relation. Hence, the stiffness change may be due to crack growth. The tests were stopped when the load exceeded 20 percent of the predicted load. The panels were subsequently cut up and it was found that the simulated cracks had grown and extended a few millimetres downward into the

core in approximately an 80 degree inclined angle. For the panel with $a = 250$ mm, a major load drop occurred at approximately 10 percent above the predicted load. In this panel the crack growth extended all the way down to the opposite face. The ratio of the predicted to the measured failure load is included in Table 3 along with the ratio of the design load to the failure load, the latter corresponding to the reduction in load bearing capacity. The design load is also here computed as the load for static core failure, appearing at the point of maximum transverse force, *i.e.*, mid way between two corners along the side of the panel.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The effect of debonding cracks on the load bearing capacity in foam core sandwich beams and panels have been investigated. Beams, and circular and square panels have been analysed using the FE-method and a simplified analytical model. The analytical model was found to agree well with FE-analyses of different circular panel geometries. The stress intensities, computed using the FE-method, of the square panels was somewhat higher than for the circular panels at the same load level. Hence, even a very simplified analysis yields a good estimation of the stress intensity. However, the model needs further refinements in order to accurately analyse the square panels. When the external pressure was applied on the same side as the debonding crack the crack surfaces closed but opened in the vicinity of the crack tip when the load was applied on the reverse side. As the sign of the Mode II stress intensity changed, depending on the load case, a dual fracture criteria was used. From a structural point of view, it is advantageous that the contact pressure between the crack surfaces induces friction which to some extent prevents the deformation and therefore increases the load for onset of damage growth. When applying the load so that the crack surfaces open up the sign of the shear stress implies damage growth along the face/core interface which has a much higher toughness than the core.

The predictions agreed well for the beam geometries, within 20 percent, and the reduction in load bearing capacity due to the debonding crack is as high as 1.6 to 3.6, even though the cracks are fairly short (1 to 4 times the core thickness). For the panels, the predictions also agree well, but the load for onset of damage growth was very hard to monitor accurately and the measured load is here quite an imprecise estimate. In the beam tests the fracture process could be traced visually whereas it was impossible to inspect any process for the embedded debondings in the panels. The stress intensities used in the predictions were estimates based on interpolations between the FE-calculations. The accuracy in the fracture toughness tests is rather low due to scatter in test results. The toughness may vary as much as ± 15 percent between different blocks of material. The reduction in load bearing capacity is also surprisingly low, between 1.6 and 2.8 for the tested geometries, considering the relatively large debondings of radii in the order of half the panel side length. The stiffness reduction in the beam cases were very low and of a magnitude that hardly could be measured experimentally. For the panels, the stiffness reductions were as much as 2 for large cracks and slender panels. In essence, the presented approach should be accurate enough for engineering design purposes when accounting for face/core interface debondings.

As a first study the problem with circular debondings in the middle of circular and square panels were chosen. These types of debondings are not what could be expected a worst case, since the debondings were simulated in regions of the panels where the transverse force is

low. Debondings close to the edges, where the transverse forces has a maximum, would be more severe and is a problem for future studies. The face on which the pressure load is applied is in compression and a debonding placed underneath this face could cause buckling of the face. This has not been treated here, but is also suggested for future studies.

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7. BIOGRAPHIES

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TABLE 1 COMPARISON BETWEEN COMPUTED STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS FOR FE-CALCULATION OF SIMPLY SUPPORTED CIRCULAR (circ) AND SQUARE PANELS (square), AND THE ANALYTICAL ESTIMATE (an) (E is Young's modulus, t component thickness and indices f and c refer to face and core, respectively)

Face	t_f (mm)	E_c (MPa)	t_c (mm)	a (mm)	K_{an}	K_{circ}	K_{square}
Aluminium	4	100	30	50	0.106	0.117	0.128
Aluminium	4	100	30	100	0.382	0.382	0.507
Aluminium	4	100	30	150	0.793	0.790	0.880
Aluminium	4	100	30	200	1.34	1.34	1.79
Aluminium	4	100	30	250	2.02	2.03	2.35
Aluminium	1	100	30	100	0.497	0.486	-
Aluminium	2	100	30	100	0.464	0.452	0.606
Aluminium	8	100	30	100	0.287	0.290	0.308
GRP*	4	100	30	100	0.428	0.421	0.555
Steel	4	100	30	100	0.348	0.349	0.461
Aluminium	4	100	15	100	0.615	0.620	0.736
Aluminium	4	100	60	100	0.175	0.196	0.219
Aluminium	4	60	30	100	0.365	0.367	0.489
Aluminium	4	200	30	100	0.406	0.406	0.529
Aluminium	2	100	15	200	3.47	3.48	-
Aluminium**	4	100	30	100	0.382	0.384	0.509

K in $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for a unit load, $p = 1$ MPa.

* Typical glass/polyester laminate

** clamped edges.

TABLE 2 FRACTURE TOUGHNESS DATA OF THE CORE MATERIAL (E is Young's modulus, μ shear modulus, and index c refer the core material)

Material	E_c (MPa)	μ_c (Mpa)	K_{IIc}^{ENF} ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$)	K_{IIc}^{CSB} ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$)
H60	55	22	0.12	0.22
H100	100	38	0.22	0.40
H200	200	76	0.44	0.76

TABLE 3 FRACTURE LOAD PREDICTIONS (pred) AND
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS (exp)
(DI corresponds to the design load, assuming core shear failure)

Face	t_f (mm)	E_c (MPa)	t_c (mm)	a (mm)	p^{pred}/p^{exp}	p^{DI}/p^{exp}
Beams in four-point bending						
Aluminium 2.0	55	30	30	30	0.99	1.64
Aluminium 3.0	100	60	30	30	1.19	2.93
Aluminium 3.0	200	30	60	60	0.89	3.63
GRP*	3.8	85	30	45	1.01	3.19
Square panels with circular embedded debondings						
Aluminium 2.0	100	15	200	200	1.0	1.6
GRP*	3.0	100	30	200	1.2	1.7
GRP*	2.0	60	15	200	1.3	1.6
GRP*	4.0	100	30	250	1.1	2.8

* GRP-face: Typical glass (WR and CSM fabric)/polyester laminate.

Figure 1 (a) A beam in four-point bending with an interfacial debonding crack situated between an inner and an outer support, and (b) a square panel with a circular embedded debonding crack.

Figure 2 Additional deformation of the sandwich panel due to the presence of the debonding crack.

Figure 3 Test specimens for measuring the fracture toughness, (a) the end-notch flexure (ENF) and (b) the cracked sandwich beam (CSB). The dashed lines indicate the crack growth directions.